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Additional data of ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from Epirus, Greece

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Abstract: A list of 79 species and morphospecies of ants collected in Epirus in April-May 2025, including 15 taxa new to this region, is given. The updated checklist of ants known from Epirus now includes 106 species.

Key words: ants, Greece, Epirus, faunistics.

INTRODUCTION

The ant fauna of Greece, with at least 322 confirmed species, is probably the richest in Europe. Studies on the ant biodiversity of this country remain incomplete, as the taxonomic status of more than 23 taxa still remains unresolved, and most of them are likely undescribed species (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2022, 2025, and our unpublished data). Besides, the exploration of previously studied regions keeps delivering new species for provinces and for the whole country (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2023) and some species occurring in neighbouring countries are expected to be present in Greece as well.

The first comprehensive checklist, comprising studies on Greek ants, was compiled by LEGAKIS (2011). In the last few years, the ant fauna of Greece has been studied more intensively as part of the inventory of ants in the Mediterranean region (see references in BOROWIEC *et al.* 2024). The first two volumes of the monograph on Greek ants (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2022, 2025) will likely enable regional research through citizen science, as evidenced by the effects of such activity in other Mediterranean countries (ARCOS 2025, DEMETRIOU *et al.* 2025).

At present, Epirus, with published records of 91 species or morphospecies, has the least-known ant fauna among Greek provinces. The only paper reporting new ant species from Epirus was based on material collected in its western administrative units, primarily from littoral to highland habitats (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018).

In this paper, we present a list of ants collected in Epirus in 2025, from April 21 to May 2, in the eastern and northern parts of this province, mostly from highland to mountain habitats, which allowed the discovery of 15 species new to Epirus and increased the list of species and morphospecies known from this province to 106.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The main method, applied at all sites, was direct sampling (hand collecting). Ant nests and individual specimens were collected on the ground, in leaf litter, under stones, in dead wood, on tree trunks and twigs. On roadsides and forest edges, ants were brushed off to the entomological umbrella. On the rocks, the ants' nests were searched in rock crevices and using a chisel. All specimens were collected by J.P.L. & J.J.C.W. van Delft and preserved in 70% ethanol. The list of collecting sites is arranged chronologically, and the list of collected species is arranged alphabetically. General range distribution of species is defined after BOROWIEC (2014) and based on resources obtained from AntMaps (JANICKI *et al.* 2016). Distribution in Greek provinces is based on recently published publications on ants of Greece (summarized in BOROWIEC & SALATA 2022, 2025) and unpublished data from the Database and Collection of Greek Ants (DCGA) preserved at the University of Wrocław. Geographical coordinates are given in decimal degrees N/E. The locality codes refer to the position in the coding system used in the DCGA preserved at the University of Wrocław. Material of the most interesting species is deposited in the Department of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Taxonomy, Mymecological Lab, Wrocław, Poland. All photos of habitats were prepared by J.J.C.W. van Delft.

LIST OF LOCALITIES

1. EPI25_1-9, Metsovo, 4.5 km NW of Metsovo, 20 IV 2025, 1357 m, 39.80589 / 21.15734, alpine grassland with some shrubs and small streams;
2. EPI25_10-18, Metsovo, 7.2 km NW of Metsovo, 20 IV 2025, 1361 m, 39.82126 / 21.13240, alpine grassland with some shrubs;
3. EPI25_19-21, Zagori, 2.7 km NE of Greveniti, 20 IV 2025, 982 m, 39.82909 / 21.01317, pine forest bordering mountain stream;
4. EPI25_22-24, Zagori, around Kamper Aga stone bridge, 20 IV 2025, 506 m, 39.72440 / 20.96298, road verge and path near old Zagori bridge over stream;
5. EPI25_25, Metsovo, Metsovo village centre, 20 IV 2025, 1157 m, 39.77100 / 21.18275, gravel parking area with old walls inside Metsovo;
6. EPI25_26-39, Zagori, 1 km S of Dilofo, 21 IV 2025, 787 m, 39.84325 / 20.76576, grassland with shrubs next to a small river;
7. EPI25_40-41, Zagori, Beloi viewpoint over Vikos Gorge, 21 IV 2025, 1398 m, 39.90498 / 20.76634, grassland with shrubs, rocks and stones;
8. EPI25_43-48, Zagori, 300 m NW of Vradeto, 21 IV 2025, 1339 m, 39.89811 / 20.77342, gravel road;
9. EPI25_52-54, Preveza, Venetian castle of Parga, 23 IV 2025, 35 m, 39.28247 / 20.39715, ruins and its surroundings;
10. EPI25_55, Preveza, NE end of the village of Parga, 23 IV 2025, 30 m, 39.28769 / 20.40261, parking lot under trees;
11. EPI25_62-79, Metsovo, 2.2 km NE of Metsovo, 26 IV 2025, 1393 m, 39.77509 / 21.20768, small grassland patches and path verges close to forest edges;

12. EPI25_80-101, Metsovo, 2.1 km NE of Metsovo, 26 IV 2025, 1395 m, 39.77597 / 21.20729, old pine forest;
13. EPI25_102-112, Ioannina, 2 km N of Loggades, 26 IV 2025, 834 m, 39.67639 / 20.93564, rocky hillside with scattered shrubs and many stones;
14. EPI25_112B-141, Zagori, 1.4 km SW of Oxya Viewpoint, Vikos Gorge, 27 IV 2025, 1295 m, 39.89745 / 20.74195, mountain pasture with some shrubs, trees and a few rock piles;
15. EPI25_142-150, Zagori, 1.2 km W of Monodendri, 27 IV 2025, 1131 m, 39.88057 / 20.73520, road verge;
16. EPI25_151-171, Zagori, 2.8 km E of Elafotopos, 27 IV 2025, 1429 m, 39.89926 / 20.72183, mountain pasture with many stones;
17. EPI25_172-185, Zagori, 2 km NW of Monodendri, 27 IV 2025, 1307 m, 39.89266 / 20.72870, mountain pasture with thickets;
18. EPI25_186-192, Metsovo, 4.5 km SW of Metsovo, 28 IV 2025, 880 m, 39.73918 / 21.14841, dense oak forest;
19. EPI25_193-207, Metsovo, 4.5 km SW of Metsovo, 28 IV 2025, 879 m, 39.73971 / 21.14803, grassland patch in oak forest;
20. EPI25_208-232, Metsovo, 6 km SW of Metsovo, 28 IV 2025, 1198 m, 39.72942 / 21.13738, alpine grassland with *Quercus* and *Juniperus*;
21. EPI25_233, Metsovo, 6.1 km NW of Metsovo, 28 IV 2025, 1396 m, 39.81383 / 21.13975, beech forest;
22. EPI25_234-246, Metsovo, 6.5 km NW of Metsovo, 28 IV 2025, 1357 m, 39.81768 / 21.13888, dry rocky slope with few shrubs;
23. EPI25_247-258, Metsovo, 6.3 km NW of Metsovo, 28 IV 2025, 1355 m, 39.81542 / 21.14049, moist grassland next to stream;
24. EPI25_289-292, Pogoni, 2.4 km SW of Delvinaki, 29 IV 2025, 608 m, 39.91935 / 20.44562, pasture with shrubs, rich in orchids;
25. EPI25_293-300, Pogoni, 775 m S of Stavroskiadi, 29 IV 2025, 880 m, 40.02766 / 20.44027, road verge with herbs and trees;
26. EPI25_301-309, Pogoni, 870 m S of Stavroskiadi, 29 IV 2025, 879 m, 40.02631 / 20.43957, deciduous forest;
27. EPI25_310-326, Pogoni, 2.2 km SE of Stavroskiadi, 29 IV 2025, 842 m, 40.02306 / 20.45934, small pastures next to road, mixed with patches of deciduous forest, mainly oak, also *Juniperus*;
28. EPI25_327-335, Pogoni, 980 m NW of Paleopirgos, 29 IV 2025, 958 m, 40.03413 / 20.47974, mountain pasture with shrubs, trees and forest edge;
29. EPI25_336-348, Zagori, 630 m N of Vradeto, 30 IV 2025, 1367 m, 39.90262 / 20.77524, mountain grassland with shrubs and large stones;
30. EPI25_349-357, Zagori, 2 km NE of Vradeto, 30 IV 2025, 1570 m, 39.91255 / 20.79125, dry riverbed and adjacent, sparsely vegetated, dry rocky slopes with a few scattered low shrubs;
31. EPI25_358-367B, Zagori, 530 m W of Koukouli, 30 IV 2025, 856 m, 39.87227 / 20.76863, deciduous forest and forest edge next to a dry small stream;
32. EPI25_368-377, Zagori, 2.9 km W of Dilofo, 30 IV 2025, 889 m, 39.84442 / 20.73329, forest and forest edge dominated by pine trees, with some deciduous trees;

33. EPI25_378-401, Konitsa, Thermal springs of Kavasila, 1 V 2025, 425 m, 40.10413 / 20.70517, dry grasslands with some shrubs and forest edge next to a broad gravel river;
34. EPI25_402-403, Konitsa, 2.3 km W of Exochi, 1 V 2025, 628 m, 40.09782 / 20.71300, nutrient poor grassland with some trees;
35. EPI25_404-413, Konitsa, 620 m SW of Kavasila, 1 V 2025, 648 m, 40.08183 / 20.70726, xerothermous, sparsely vegetated open spot between deciduous shrubs;
36. EPI25_414-432, Konitsa, NW of Konitsa, 1 V 2025, 470 m, 40.05075 / 20.73283, dirt road, verges, wooded patches and small grasslands in a small river valley;
37. EPI25_433-444, Konitsa, 2 km SW of Konitsa, 1 V 2025, 476 m, 40.03278 / 20.73191, grassland with some shrubs and trees;
38. EPI25_446-466, Metsovo, 7.2 km N of Metsovo, 2 V 2025, 1478 m, 39.83402 / 21.18809, pine forest and forest edge;
39. EPI25_445, Zagori, Ano Pedina, IV 2025, 1012 m, 39.88249 / 20.70811, small old Zagori village.

LIST OF COLLECTED SPECIES

(species new to the fauna of Epirus marked with an asterisk)

1. *Aphaenogaster balcanica* (EMERY, 1898)

Localities: 4, 6, 9, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 19, 20, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 39.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species, in Greece recorded from all provinces except Crete.

2. *Aphaenogaster epirotes* (EMERY, 1895)

Localities: 15, 27, 36, 37.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species, recorded from all mainland provinces, the Cyclades, the Eastern Aegean Islands, and the Ionian Islands.

3. *Aphaenogaster subterranea* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 18, 26, 32.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species, in Greece recorded from all provinces except Crete. In our previous paper on ants of Epirus (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018: 4), it was recorded under the name *Aphaenogaster* cf. *subterranea* due to the occurrence of two distinct morphotypes separated by habitat preferences. The most recent revision of this complex (ZIĘCINA *et al.* 2024) showed that both forms represent only two ecotypes of a single species.

4. *Aphaenogaster subterraneoides* EMERY, 1881*

Locality: 37.

Distribution in Greece: *A. subterraneoides* is a rare species mainly noted from island provinces, in mainland Greece known only from a single record in Thrace (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2023) and is now reported as new to Epirus.

5. *Bothriomyrmex communista* SANTSCHI, 1919

Localities: 11, 16, 20, 22, 24, 29, 30, 31, 33, 35, 36, 38.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species, in Greece recorded from all provinces except Crete.

6. *Camponotus aethiops* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 6, 11, 13, 14, 19, 20, 24, 25, 28, 29, 31, 36, 37.

Distribution in Greece: It is a very common species, in Greece recorded from all provinces.

7. *Camponotus dalmaticus* (NYLANDER, 1849)

Localities: 26, 31, 35, 36.

Distribution in Greece: It is a predominantly northern and western species in Greece, known from all mainland provinces, the East Aegean Islands, and the Ionian Islands.

8. *Camponotus fallax* (NYLANDER, 1856)

Localities: 25, 28.

Distribution in Greece: It is an uncommon species in mainland Greece and a rare species on the islands, recorded from the East Aegean Islands, the Ionian Islands, and the Dodecanese.

9. *Camponotus gestroi* EMERY, 1878*

Localities: 9, 24, 27, 28, 33, 34.

Distribution in Greece: It is an uncommon species recorded from all provinces except Epirus. Our records are the first for the Epirus province.

10. *Camponotus heidrunvogtae* SEIFERT, 2019

Locality: 24.

Distribution in Greece: It is a recently described species, known from the Ionian Islands, Epirus, Macedonia and Sterea Ellas. In our previous paper on ants of Epirus (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018: 5), recorded as *Camponotus* cf. *piceus*.

11. *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER, 1792)

Localities: 9, 36.

Distribution in Greece: It is one of the most common Greek species of *Camponotus* recorded from all regions, but appears to be rare in Epirus.

12. *Camponotus oertzeni* FOREL, 1889

Localities: 11, 13, 15, 17, 19, 22, 24, 27, 31, 35.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common Greek species often misidentified with *Camponotus aethiops*, known from all provinces except the Cyclades.

13. *Camponotus piceus* (LEACH, 1825)

Localities: 2, 11, 15, 16, 17, 22, 25, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 35, 37, 38.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands, rare in Crete and the East Aegean Islands.

14. *Camponotus vagus* (SCOPOLI, 1763)

Localities: 4, 14, 17, 22, 29, 32, 33, 38, 39.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands, rare in Crete and the East Aegean Islands.

15. *Cataglyphis nodus* (BRULLÉ, 1833)

Localities: 24, 27, 33, 34, 35, 36.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species recorded from most regions except the Cyclades, with one doubtful record from Crete.

16. *Chalepoxenus muellerianus* (FINZI, 1922)

Localities: 27, 29.

Distribution in Greece: It is an uncommon species, a social parasite in nests of various

Temnothorax species, particularly those in the *T. recedens* group. In Greece, it was noted from all mainland provinces except Thrace, Crete and the Ionian Islands. In Epirus, we found it in nests of *Temnothorax recedens* and *T. cf. tuberculum*_long spine, both times between two stones/rocks.

17. ***Colobopsis truncata*** (SPINOLA, 1808)

Localities: 25, 36.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species recorded from all regions.

18. ***Crematogaster schmidti*** (MAYR, 1853)

Localities: 9, 13, 24, 25, 28, 31, 34, 36, 37, 39.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in the north and central mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands, rare in the southern mainland, and the East Aegean Islands. A single record from Crete in urban area is based probably on an introduced colony.

19. ***Crematogaster sordidula*** (NYLANDER, 1849)

Localities: 13, 24, 35.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species recorded from all Greek provinces.

20. ***Dolichoderus quadripunctatus*** (LINNAEUS, 1771)

Localities: 10, 18, 25, 26, 28, 35, 36, 37.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species recorded from most regions, except Crete and the Cyclades.

21. ***Formica cinerea*** MAYR, 1853

Locality: 23.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare species known only from northern Greece, recorded from Epirus, Macedonia, Thessaly and Thrace.

22. ***Formica clara*** FOREL, 1886

Locality: 8.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland, in the islands, known only from the East Aegean Islands.

23. ***Formica cunicularia*** LATREILLE, 1798

Localities: 11, 20, 29, 39.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in the northern mainland, uncommon in the southern mainland, and in the islands known only from Crete and the Ionian Islands.

24. ***Formica fusca*** LINNAEUS, 1758

Localities: 6, 8, 14, 23, 32.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species on the Greek mainland's mountains, and in the islands known only from Crete and the Ionian Islands.

25. ***Formica gagates*** LATREILLE, 1798

Localities: 26, 27, 28, 31, 39.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species on the Greek mainland, and in the islands known only from the East Aegean Islands and the Ionian Islands.

26. ***Formica pratensis*** RETZIUS, 1783*

Localities: 1, 17.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare species in Greece, known only from high altitudes in the mountains of Macedonia, Thessaly and Thrace. New to Epirus.

27. *Formica rufibarbis* FABRICIUS, 1793

Localities: 1, 2, 5, 6, 11, 29.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland, in the islands known only from the Cyclades and the East Aegean Islands.

28. *Formica sanguinea* LATREILLE, 1798*

Locality: 11.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare species in Greece, known only from the high altitudes in the mountains of Macedonia, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace. We found one nest, situated under a stone. In the colony, *Formica cunicularia* was present as an enslaved species. New to Epirus.

29. *Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER, 1850)

Localities: 12, 14, 16, 17, 29, 30, 32, 38.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in the northern mainland, uncommon in the southern mainland and islands.

30. *Lasius balcanicus* / *distinguendus**

Localities: 1, 6, 14, 19.

Note: A proper identification of *Lasius balcanicus* and *L. distinguendus* is possible only based on gyne characters. In Epirus, only workers were collected.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare complex in Greece, known only from Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thrace. New to Epirus.

31. *Lasius bombycina* SEIFERT & GALKOWSKI, 2016

Localities: 1, 2, 6, 7, 15, 19, 22, 23, 27, 28.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland, in islands known only from the Ionian Islands.

32. *Lasius brunneus* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 21, 39.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species in the mountains of the Greek mainland and on the islands, known only from the East Aegean and Ionian Islands.

33. *Lasius flavus* (FABRICIUS, 1782)

Localities: 2, 6, 11, 12, 14, 17, 19, 20, 23, 27, 31, 32, 38.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in the mountains of the Greek mainland, in islands known only from the East Aegean Islands and the Ionian Islands.

34. *Lasius illyricus* ZIMMERMANN, 1935

Localities: 11, 12, 17, 20, 25, 26, 27, 32.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species in the mountains of the Greek mainland and on islands known only from Crete and the East Aegean Islands.

35. *Lasius myops* FOREL, 1894*

Localities: 7, 19, 27.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare species in Greece, known only from Macedonia, Thessaly and Thrace. New to Epirus.

36. *Lasius psammophilus* SEIFERT, 1992

Locality: 38.

Distribution in Greece: It is the most common *Lasius* species in the alpine areas of the mountains along western Macedonia, Thessaly and Epirus.

37. *Lasius sabularum* (BONDROIT, 1918)*

Localities: 1, 12, 18, 22, 23.

Distribution in Greece: It is a very rare species in Greece, recently recorded from Thrace (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2023) and Thessaly (BOROWIEC *et al.* 2024). New to Epirus.

38. *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* (MAYR, 1855)

Locality: 9.

Distribution in Greece: This species was recorded from all Greek provinces except the Cyclades, but according to BOROWIEC & SALATA (2022), it is probably a complex of cryptic taxa, and requires revision based on morphometric and molecular studies. The Epirus populations have characteristics of the typical form known from the northern mainland provinces.

39. *Lepisiota melas* (EMERY, 1915)*

Locality: 9.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species but known from almost all Greek provinces. New to Epirus.

40. *Liometopum microcephalum* (PANZER, 1798)

Localities: 34, 35.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species in Greek mainland, in islands known only from the East Aegean Islands and the Ionian Islands.

41. *Messor hellenius* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987

Localities: 4, 9, 36, 37.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species but known from all Greek provinces. In Epirus, the predominant form has a reduced striate sculpture on the head.

42. *Messor ibericus* SANTSCHI, 1931

Locality: 20.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species but known from all Greek provinces except the Cyclades.

43. *Messor structor* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 8, 9, 13, 15, 16, 20, 24, 25, 28, 30, 31, 36, 39.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in mountains of all mainland provinces.

44. *Messor wasmanni* KRAUSSE, 1910

Localities: 9, 13, 33.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species recorded from all Greek provinces.

45. *Myrmecina graminicola* (LATREILLE, 1802)

Localities: 26, 27, 38.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland, rare in island provinces, not recorded from the East Aegean Islands.

46. *Myrmica hellenica* FINZI, 1926*

Locality: 6.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare species known only from the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Thessaly and Thrace. New to Epirus.

47. *Myrmica ravasinii* FINZI, 1923

Locality: 12.

Distribution in Greece: It is a very rare species, few confirmed records are known only from Albania, Armenia, Caucasian Russia, Georgia, Greece, Serbia and Türkiye. From Greece, it was recorded only from a single locality in Metsovo regional unit of Epirus and from Tzoumerka Mts. at the border area between Epirus and Thessaly (SEIFERT 2003, RADCHENKO *et al.* 2016). Our record confirmed its occurrence in the Metsovo area. Three nests were found at this site at small open spaces in old pine forest; two ground nests and one not further specified nest.

48. *Myrmica sabuleti* MEINERT, 1861

Localities: 2, 3, 11, 12, 14, 27, 38.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland.

49. *Myrmica scabrinodis* NYLANDER, 1846*

Locality: 23.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland and the Ionian Islands. First record from Epirus.

50. *Myrmoxenus menozzii* FINZI, 1924*

Locality: 14.

Distribution in Greece: Known from the Aegean Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly. It is a rare species, a social parasite in nests of various species of the genus *Temnothorax*. In Greece, observed in nests of *Temnothorax lichtensteini*, *Temnothorax unifasciatus* and *Temnothorax cf. tuberum*. In Epirus, collected in the nest of *Temnothorax lichtensteini* located between two stones. First record from Epirus.

51. *Pheidole cf. pallidula* complex

Localities: 6, 13, 15, 19, 24, 25, 27, 31, 39.

Note: The Mediterranean populations of the taxon named *Pheidole pallidula* (NYLANDER, 1849) have recently been divided into four species, three of which were recorded in Greece (SEIFERT 2016). However, this point of view remains under discussion owing to the substantial local variability of this common Mediterranean ant. In the Greek material examined by B. Seifert, there were no specimens from Epirus, but from the neighboring regions of western Greece (the Ionian Islands, the NW Peloponnese) the author noted *P. balcanica* SEIFERT. The small number of major workers from Epirus precludes precise identification, so we report them as *Pheidole cf. pallidula* complex.

Distribution in Greece: This complex of taxa belongs to one of the commonest ants in Greece, recorded from all provinces.

52. *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 2, 11, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 20, 22, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 30, 31, 32, 36.

Distribution in Greece: It is a very common species recorded from all Greek provinces.

53. *Plagiolepis taurica* SANTSCHI, 1920*

Localities: 1, 22, 33, 35, 38.

Note: According to KIRSCHNER *et al.* (2023), *Plagiolepis taurica* SANTSCHI, 1920, occurs in the western part of mainland Greece. Re-examination of our materials of this species group from Greece and Cyprus indicated the presence of two species in Greece, *P. taurica* and *P. pallescens* FOREL, 1889. The latter is probably more eastern in distribution, and its confirmed samples are from the Dodecanese and Cyprus. Another species from this group occurs in Cyprus, but its status is currently under investigation.

Distribution in Greece: *Plagiolepis taurica* is known in Greece from all mainland provinces except Sterea Ellas and from the East Aegean Islands and the Ionian Islands. First record from Epirus.

54. *Plagiolepis xene* STÄRCKE, 1936

Locality: 31.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare social parasite in nests of various species of the genus *Plagiolepis*, and is known from the East Aegean islands, Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Thessaly and Macedonia. In Epirus, it was observed in a nest of *P. pygmaea*.

55. *Ponera coarctata* (LATREILLE, 1802)

Localities: 1, 2, 3, 18, 20, 23, 27, 30, 32.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland, the East Aegean Islands, and the Ionian Islands.

56. *Ponera testacea* EMERY, 1895*

Locality: 11.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare species recorded from the East Aegean Islands, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace. New to Epirus.

57. *Prenolepis nitens* (MAYR, 1853)

Localities: 15, 18, 24, 26, 28, 31, 35, 36.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species in the Greek mainland, the East Aegean Islands, and the Ionian Islands.

58. *Proformica* cf. *oculatissima**

Locality: 30.

Note: *Proformica oculatissima* (FOREL, 1886) is a rare, and recently redescribed species (LEBAS & GALKOWSKI 2019) known from the Ionian Islands, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas and Thessaly. However, LEBAS (2025) suggested that this group is more speciose in Greece and probably contains three cryptic taxa. Based on the available key for identifying Greek *Proformica* (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2022, 2025), the specimen from Epirus falls into the taxon *P. oculatissima* but we collected only one minor specimen and proper identification based on a single specimen is practically impossible, therefore we noted this taxon only as a member of the *P. cf. oculatissima* complex.

Distribution in Greece: First record for this complex from Epirus.

59. *Solenopsis juliae* (ARAKELIAN, 1991)

Localities: 1, 2, 6, 11, 16, 17, 19, 20, 26, 27, 30, 31, 32, 33, 36, 37.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species known from all provinces except Crete.

60. *Stenamma debile* (FÖRSTER, 1850)

Localities: 12.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species known from most of the mainland provinces except Thrace, and from Crete, the Cyclades and the Ionian Islands.

61. *Stenamma striatulum* EMERY, 1895

Locality: 18, 31.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare species known only from Epirus, Macedonia and the Peloponnese.

62. *Tapinoma glabrellum* NYLANDER, 1849

Localities: 1, 2, 12, 13, 14, 16, 17, 19, 20, 24, 25, 28, 29, 30, 33, 36, 37, 38.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species recorded from all Greek provinces. In the previous paper on ants from Epirus (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018) noted under the name *Tapinoma erraticum*.

63. *Temnothorax albipennis* (CURTIS, 1854)

Localities: 14, 17, 19.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare species noted only from mountains of Epirus, the Peloponnese and Thessaly. In the previous paper on ants from Epirus (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018), it was noted under the name *Temnothorax* cf. *albipennis*.

64. *Temnothorax balcanicus* (SANTSCHI, 1909)

Localities: 16, 20.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species recorded from all provinces except the Ionian Islands. In all previous papers, this taxon was recorded from Greece under the name *Temnothorax semiruber* (ANDRÉ, 1881). The recent revision of the *Temnothorax rottenbergii* species group showed that *T. balcanicus* and *T. semiruber* are closely related but distinct species (CSÓSZ *et al.* 2025). True *T. semiruber* is known from western Turkey and Levant, and its occurrence in the southeastern Aegean Islands is possible.

65. *Temnothorax brackoi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2019

Localities: 31, 35, 36.

Distribution in Greece: It is a recently described species that appears to be common in northwestern and western Greece. Recorded from Epirus, the Ionian Islands, the Peloponnese, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace. In the previous paper on ants from Epirus (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018) it was noted under the name *Temnothorax* cf. *tauricus*.

66. *Temnothorax crassispinus* (KARAVAIEV, 1926)

Localities: 12, 14, 27.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in the western mainland and the Ionian Islands.

67. *Temnothorax lichtensteini* (BONDROIT, 1918)

Localities: 14, 17, 26, 27, 31.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common species in northern and central Greece, recorded from the East Aegean Islands, Epirus, the Ionian Islands, Macedonia, Sterea Ellas, Thessaly and Thrace.

68. *Temnothorax parvulus* (SCHENCK, 1852)

Locality: 14.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare species in Greece, recorded from all mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands.

69. *Temnothorax recedens* (NYLANDER, 1856)

Localities: 14, 27.

Distribution in Greece: It is the most common Greek member of the genus *Temnothorax*, known from all provinces.

70. *Temnothorax tergestinus* (FINZI, 1928)

Localities: 5, 12, 17.

Distribution in Greece: It is a rare species in Greece, recorded from Epirus, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Thessaly and Thrace.

71. *Temnothorax* cf. *tubерum*_long spine

Localities: 8, 11, 16, 17, 20, 27, 28, 29, 30, 32, 33.

Note: Greek species of the *Temnothorax* *tubерum* complex require revision. Populations from Greece differ from populations from Central Europe and perhaps represent other cryptic species. *Temnothorax* cf. *tubерum*_long spine is characterized by extremely long propodeal spines.

Distribution in Greece: This taxon is common in all mountain regions of mainland Greece and the Ionian Islands.

72. *Temnothorax turcicus* (SANTSCHI, 1934)

Localities: 25, 27, 28, 31, 35.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common arboreal species known from all mainland provinces and the East Aegean Islands. In the previous paper on ants from Epirus (BOROWIEC & SALATA 2018) it was noted under the name *Temnothorax* cf. *turcicus*.

73. *Temnothorax unifasciatus* (LATREILLE, 1798)

Localities: 11, 14, 27.

Note: Recently Csősz *et al.* (2024) revised *Temnothorax unifasciatus* complex and concluded that it contains only two species: *T. unifasciatus* (LATREILLE, 1798) and *T. brackoi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2019, but they studied only three Greek specimens from a single locality for *T. unifasciatus* but, according to our unpublished data, this complex in Greece is more diverse than in other parts of Europe. This revision also does not take into account the biological differences between the morphotypes observed in Greece, and it may be necessary to restore *Temnothorax tauricus* (RUZSKY, 1902) from the synonyms of *T. unifasciatus*.

Distribution in Greece: The Greek species of the *Temnothorax unifasciatus* complex require revision (see note above). Some populations from Greece slightly differ from populations of Central Europe and perhaps represent a few cryptic species. The samples noted in this paper appear to be typical *T. unifasciatus*.

74. *Tetramorium caespitum* (LINNAEUS, 1758)

Localities: 1, 6, 20, 23, 29, 30, 36, 38.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species recorded from the mountains of Epirus, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, Thessaly and Thrace. It is the least thermophilic species of the *T. caespitum* complex.

75. *Tetramorium diomedeam* EMERY, 1908

Locality: 35.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species recorded from all Greek provinces except Sterea Ellas.

76. *Tetramorium impurum* (FÖRSTER, 1850)

Localities: 1, 16, 23, 29.

Distribution in Greece: It is a common, mostly mountain species, recorded from all mainland provinces and the Ionian Islands.

77. *Tetramorium indocile* SANTSCHI, 1927*

Localities: 11, 14, 20, 22, 23, 28, 37.

Distribution in Greece: It is the most thermophilic species in the *T. caespitum* complex,

recorded from sunny and dry habitats, also from mountain steppes. Hitherto recorded from the Aegean Islands, Crete, the Dodecanese, Macedonia, the Peloponnese, and Thessaly. New to Epirus.

78. *Tetramorium kephalosi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2017

Localities: 9, 13, 33, 35, 36.

Distribution in Greece: It is the most common Greek member of the genus *Tetramorium*, recorded from all provinces.

79. *Tetramorium moravicum* KRATOCHVIL, 1941

Localities: 1, 2, 3, 6, 11, 14, 16, 22, 23, 25, 29, 30, 36.

Distribution in Greece: It is a moderately common species recorded from all mainland provinces.

UPDATED CHECKLIST OF ANTS OF EPIRUS

(Species new to Epirus in bold)

1. *Aphaenogaster balcanica* (EMERY, 1898)
2. *Aphaenogaster epirotes* (EMERY, 1895)
3. *Aphaenogaster ovaticeps* (EMERY, 1898)
4. *Aphaenogaster subterranea* (LATREILLE, 1798)
5. ***Aphaenogaster subterraneoides*** EMERY, 1881
6. *Bothriomyrmex communista* SANTSCHI, 1919
7. *Camponotus aethiops* (LATREILLE, 1798)
8. *Camponotus atricolor* (NYLANDER, 1849)
9. *Camponotus dalmaticus* (NYLANDER, 1849)
10. *Camponotus fallax* (NYLANDER, 1856)
11. ***Camponotus gestroi*** EMERY, 1878
12. *Camponotus heidrunvogtae* SEIFERT, 2019
13. *Camponotus ionius* EMERY, 1920
14. *Camponotus lateralis* (OLIVIER, 1792)
15. *Camponotus ligniperda* (LATREILLE, 1802)
16. *Camponotus oertzeni* FOREL, 1889
17. *Camponotus piceus* (LEACH, 1825)
18. *Camponotus vagus* (SCOPOLI, 1763)
16. *Cataglyphis nodus* (BRULLÉ, 1833)
17. *Chalepoxenus muellerianus* (FINZI, 1922)
18. *Colobopsis truncata* (SPINOLA, 1808)
19. *Crematogaster* cf. *ionia* complex
20. *Crematogaster schmidti* (MAYR, 1853)
21. *Crematogaster sordidula* (NYLANDER, 1849)
22. *Dolichoderus quadripunctatus* (LINNAEUS, 1771)
23. *Formica cinerea* MAYR, 1853

24. *Formica clara* FOREL, 1886
25. *Formica cunicularia* LATREILLE, 1798
26. *Formica fusca* LINNAEUS, 1758
27. *Formica gagates* LATREILLE, 1798
28. *Formica lugubris* ZETTERSTEDT, 1838
29. ***Formica pratensis*** RETZIUS, 1783
30. *Formica rufibarbis* FABRICIUS, 1793
31. ***Formica sanguinea*** LATREILLE, 1798
32. *Hypoponera eduardi* (FOREL, 1894)
33. *Lasius alienus* (FÖRSTER, 1850)
34. ***Lasius balcanicus*** and ***distinguendus*** complex
35. *Lasius bombycina* SEIFERT & GALKOWSKI, 2016
36. *Lasius brunneus* (LATREILLE, 1798)
37. *Lasius citrinus* EMERY, 1922
38. *Lasius emarginatus* (OLIVIER, 1792)
39. *Lasius flavus* (FABRICIUS, 1782)
40. *Lasius illyricus* ZIMMERMANN, 1935
41. *Lasius lasioides* (EMERY, 1869)
42. *Lasius mixtus* (NYLANDER, 1846)
43. ***Lasius myops*** FOREL, 1894
44. *Lasius paralienus* SEIFERT, 1992
45. *Lasius psammophilus* SEIFERT, 1992
46. ***Lasius sabularum*** (BONDROIT, 1918)
47. *Lasius turcicus* SANTSCHI, 1921
48. *Lepisiota frauenfeldi* (MAYR, 1855)
49. ***Lepisiota melas*** (EMERY, 1915)
50. *Liometopum microcephalum* (PANZER, 1798)
51. *Messor atanassovii* ATANASSOV, 1982
52. *Messor hellenius* AGOSTI & COLLINGWOOD, 1987
53. *Messor ibericus* SANTSCHI, 1931
54. *Messor structor* (LATREILLE, 1798)
55. *Messor wasmanni* KRAUSSE, 1910
56. *Monomorium monomorium* BOLTON, 1987
57. *Myrmecina graminicola* (LATREILLE, 1802)
58. *Myrmica constricta* KARAVAIEV, 1934
59. ***Myrmica hellenica*** FINZI, 1926
60. *Myrmica ravasinii* FINZI, 1923
61. *Myrmica ruginodis* NYLANDER, 1846
62. *Myrmica sabuleti* MEINERT, 1861

63. *Myrmica scabrinodis* NYLANDER, 1846
64. *Myrmoxenus menozzi* FINZI, 1924
65. *Myrmoxenus ravouxi* (ANDRÉ, 1896)
66. *Pheidole* cf. *pallidula* complex
67. *Plagiolepis perperamus* SALATA, BOROWIEC & RADCHENKO, 2018
68. *Plagiolepis pygmaea* (LATREILLE, 1798)
69. ***Plagiolepis taurica*** SANTSCHI, 1920
70. *Plagiolepis xene* STÄRCKE, 1936
71. *Ponera coarctata* (LATREILLE, 1802)
72. ***Ponera testacea*** EMERY, 1895
73. *Prenolepis nitens* (MAYR, 1853)
74. *Proceratium algericum* FOREL, 1899
75. ***Proformica*** cf. ***oculatissima***
76. *Solenopsis juliae* (ARAKELIAN, 1991)
77. *Stenammas debile* (FÖRSTER, 1850)
78. *Stenammas striatulum* EMERY, 1895
79. *Stigmatomma denticulatum* ROGER, 1859
80. *Strumigenys bauduieri* (EMERY, 1875)
81. *Strumigenys membranifera* EMERY, 1869
82. *Tapinoma glabellum* NYLANDER, 1849
83. *Temnothorax affinis* (MAYR, 1855)
84. *Temnothorax albipennis* (CURTIS, 1854)
85. *Temnothorax balcanicus* (ANDRÉ, 1881)
86. *Temnothorax brackoi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2019
87. *Temnothorax bulgaricus* (FOREL, 1892)
88. *Temnothorax crassispinus* (KARAVAEV, 1926)
89. *Temnothorax exilis* (EMERY, 1869)
90. *Temnothorax jailensis* (ARNOLDI, 1977)
91. *Temnothorax lichtensteini* (BONDROIT, 1918)
92. *Temnothorax morea* CSÖSZ, SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2018
93. *Temnothorax parvulus* (SCHENCK, 1852)
94. *Temnothorax recedens* (NYLANDER, 1856)
95. *Temnothorax rogeri* EMERY, 1869
96. *Temnothorax tergestinus* (FINZI, 1928)
97. *Temnothorax turcicus* (SANTSCHI, 1934)
98. *Temnothorax* cf. *tuberum*_long spine
99. *Temnothorax unifasciatus* (LATREILLE, 1798)
100. *Tetramorium breviscapus* WAGNER *et al.*, 2017
101. *Tetramorium caespitum* (LINNAEUS, 1758)

102. *Tetramorium diomedeam* EMERY, 1908
103. *Tetramorium impurum* (FÖRSTER, 1850)
104. ***Tetramorium indocile*** SANTSCHI, 1927
105. *Tetramorium kephalosi* SALATA & BOROWIEC, 2017
106. *Tetramorium moravicum* KRATOCHVIL, 1941

REFERENCES

- ARCOS J. 2025. Citizen science meets Myrmecology: a systematic review of iNaturalist's contribution to ant research. *Iberomyrmex* 14: DOI: 10.20350/digitalCSIC/17721.
- BOROWIEC L. 2014. Catalogue of ants of Europe, the Mediterranean Basin and adjacent regions (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Genus* (monograph) 25: 1–340.
- BOROWIEC L., SALATA S. 2018. New records of ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from Epirus, Greece. *Acta entomologica silesiana* 26(001): 1–22 [online]. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1169150.
- BOROWIEC L., SALATA S. 2022. A monographic review of ants of Greece (Hymenoptera: Formicinae). Vol. 1. Introduction and review of all subfamilies except the subfamily Myrmicinae. *Natural History Monographs of the Upper Silesian Museum* 1: Part 1: Text 1–297 pp., part 2: Plates 299–757 pp.
- BOROWIEC L., SALATA S. 2025. A monographic review of ants of Greece (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). Vol. 2. Review of the subfamily Myrmicinae except the genus *Temnothorax* and *Tetramorium*. *Natural History Monographs of the Upper Silesian Museum* 3: part 1: Text: 1–476 pp., part 2: Plates: 477–976 pp.
- BOROWIEC L., VAN DELFT J.P.L., VAN DELFT J.C.W., SALATA S. 2023. Five ant species (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) new to the Greek fauna with notes on ants from Greek Thrace. *Annals of the Upper Silesian Museum in Bytom, Entomology* 32(008): 1–13 [online]. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10101028.
- BOROWIEC L., SALATA S., ZIĘCINA D. 2024. Ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) of the Agrafta mountain region in Greece, with additional data on ants from western Thessaly. *Annals of the Upper Silesian Museum Bytom, Entomology* 33(008): 1–28 [online]. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13960579.
- CSÓSZ S., ALICATA A., BÁTHORI F., GALKOWSKI C., SCHIFANI E., YUSUPOV Z., HERCZEG G., PREBUS M.M. 2024. Integrative taxonomy reveals inflated biodiversity in the European *Temnothorax unifasciatus* complex (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Zoologica Scripta* 53(5): 17 pp.
- CSÓSZ S., TAHERI A., SCHIFANI E., REYES-LOPEZ J.-L., ALICATA A., BÁTHORI F., PREBUS M.M. 2025. Taxonomic revision of the Mediterranean *Temnothorax rottenbergii* species group via integrated morphological and molecular approaches. *Insect Systematics and Diversity* 9(6): ixaf045.
- DEMETRIOU J., BOROWIEC L., GEORGIADES C., ECONOMO E.P., ROY E.H., MARTINO A.F., SALATA S. 2025. Citizen-science supplements species inventories and reveals the invasion of *Monomorium exiguum* and *Pheidole parva* (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) in Cyprus. *Sociobiology* 72(3): e11594: 1–10.
- JANICKI J., NARULA N., ZIEGLER M., GUÉNARD B., ECONOMO E.P. 2016. Visualizing and interacting with large-volume biodiversity data using client-server web-mapping applications: The design and implementation of antmaps.org. *Ecological Informatics* 32: 185–193.
- KIRSCHNER P., SEIFERT B., KRÖLL J., THE STEPPE CONSORTIUM, SCLICK-STEINER B.C., STEINER F.M. 2023. Phylogenomic inference and demographic model selection suggest peripatric separation of the cryptic steppe ant species *Plagiolepis pyrenaica* stat. rev. *Molecular Ecology* 32: 1149–1168.
- LEBAS C. 2025. Description de *Proformica christophii*, nouvelle espèce du genre *Proformica* RUZSKY, 1902 en Grèce (Hymenoptera, Formicidae). *Revue de l'Association Roussillonnaise d'Entomologie* 116 : 82–87.
- LEBAS C., GALKOWSKI C. 2019. Notes sur le genre *Proformica* RUZSKY, 1902 (Hymenoptera, Formicidae): redécouverte en Grèce de *Proformica oculatissima* (FOREL, 1886). *Bulletin de la Société linnéenne de Bordeaux, nouv. série* 47(3/4): 293–298.
- RADCHENKO A., YUSUPOV Z., KOMAROV Y. 2016. New data on the distribution and ecology of *Myrmica ravaninii* FINZI, 1923 (Hymenoptera, Formicidae). *Asian Myrmecology* 8: 1–7.
- SEIFERT B. 2003. The Palaearctic members of the *Myrmica schencki* group with description of a new species (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Beiträge zur Entomologie* 53: 141–159.
- ZIĘCINA D., MENCHETTI M., BOROWIEC L., BRAČKO G., LAPEVA-GJONOVA A., VILA R., SALATA S. 2024. Taxonomic revision of the *Aphaenogaster subterranea* species group (Hymenoptera, Formicidae). *Annales Zoologici* 74: 237–282.

Fig. 1. Map of collecting sites (black circles).

Figs. 2–3. Fig. 2: Locality 1. Grasslands with scattered shrubs and small streams in the Metsovo region. This habitat hosts *Formica pratensis* and *Lasius sabularum*, both recorded here for the first time in Epirus. Fig. 3: Locality 7. The Beloi viewpoint overlooking the impressive Vikos Gorge. In the grassland with shrubs, rocks, and stones located just before the viewpoint, *Lasius myops* was collected, another species newly recorded for Epirus.

Figs. 4–5. Fig. 4: Locality 11. Small grassland patches and path verges situated along forest edges. At this locality, *Formica sanguinea* and *Ponera testacea* were recorded, both representing new findings for Epirus. Fig. 5: Locality 12. Old pine forest located 2.1 km northeast of Metsovo. Here, *Myrmica ravaninii*, *Lasius sabularum* (new to Epirus), and *Temnothorax tergestinus* were collected. *M. ravaninii* occurred in slightly more open spots within the forest, as shown in Fig. 5.

Figs. 6–7. Fig. 6: Locality 12. Old pine forest located 2.1 km northeast of Metsovo. *Lasius sabularum* was found here in the more closed, shaded parts of the forest, as shown in Fig. 6. Fig. 7: Locality 12. Nest entrance of *Myrmica ruginodis*, shown slightly damaged from the collecting process. The entrance consisted of intertwined mud and dead plant material.

Figs. 8–9. Locality 14. Fig. 8: Mountain pasture with scattered shrubs, trees, and several small rock piles. At this site, *Myrmoxenus menozzii* (new to Epirus), *Temnothorax albipennis*, and *T. parvulus* were recorded. Fig. 9: Collecting site of *Myrmoxenus menozzii*, which was found between the photographed rocks.

Figs. 10–11. Fig. 10: Locality 17. Mountain pasture with dense thickets. At this site, *Formica pratensis* (new to Epirus), *Temnothorax albipennis*, and *T. tergestinus* were recorded. Fig. 11: Locality 23. Moist grassland adjacent to a stream, where *Formica cinerea* and *Lasius sabularum* (new to Epirus) were found.

Figs. 12–13. Fig. 12: Locality 27. Small pastures along a roadside, interspersed with patches of deciduous forest (mainly oak), with some *Juniperus*. This site is the habitat of *Chalepoxenus muellerianus* (found between the rocks shown here) and of *Lasius myops* (new to Epirus). Fig. 13: Locality 30. Dry riverbed with adjacent, sparsely vegetated rocky slopes and scattered low shrubs in the Zagori region. *Proformica* cf. *oculatissima* was recorded here for the first time in Epirus.

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